

SMART-RAD: AN INNOVATIVE GROUND PENETRATING RADAR FOR BURIED OBJECTS DETECTION AND RECOGNITION

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ABSTRACT

The SMART-RAD project is an EC funded RTD project aiming to the development of an evolutionary Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) system, specifically designed for the identification and recognition of buried objects in a fast, accurate and user-friendly way. The innovative features of the SMART-RAD system will allow to overcome the principal limitations of currently marketed system, that still limit the diffusion of the GPR techniques for subsurface monitoring within the construction industry. Thanks to improved measurement performance, fast and reliable survey techniques and innovative real-time data interpretation capabilities, the SMART-RAD system will finally bring the GPR instrument to become the standard tool for non-invasive ground monitoring in all the fields related to the construction and excavation industry.

1. PROJECT OVERVIEW

The SMART-RAD project intends to develop an innovative GPR technology able to set forth the conditions for a widespread commercialisation of GPR tools within the broad range of industrial fields where efficient and cost-effective subsurface analysis is required.

1.1. Background

Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) is one of the most promising methods for inspection of objects and features lying beneath the ground. Most optically opaque surfaces, such as the ground, are in fact more transparent to low frequency electromagnetic radiation. E.M. waves with frequency below 1 GHz can penetrate into the Earth surface down to several meters, with an attenuation proportional to the host material conductivity and to the frequency itself. GPR systems transmit short electromagnetic pulses into the ground through a wide-band transmitting antenna, usually dragged over the surveyed area. Dielectric discontinuities caused by contacts between different underground materials produce reflection (back scattering) of the impinging electromagnetic waves towards the surface. The GPR receiving antenna records such reflections from the ground and from buried objects while moving the system along the track. By taking regularly spaced acquisitions, an image representing a vertical slice of the ground is obtained.

Based on this principle, first pulsed GPR systems were developed in the 1950-1960s and ap-

plied to the detection and thickness mapping of subsurface geologic features and strata. In recent years the use of GPR as a tool for buried object detection and identification has been suggested, mainly within US co-operative research projects. In response to the growing interest shown by civil sector industries (gas, electricity, water, telecommunications and oil companies) in the information that can be derived from GPR exploration, commercial systems have been developed both in Europe and US during the last two decades. These systems have proven to be valid alternatives to conventional underground inspection techniques allowing non-destructive analysis of buried objects and features.

The good results achieved suggest that an evolutionary design process could widen the market to the whole sector of civil engineering and construction industries. In fact subsurface maps of construction sites showing presence and location of shallow buried objects could be obtained by GPR surveys before and during excavation works. These maps might be of great help in the prevention of damages to underground pipes and tubes and of accidents due to crashes of risky lines (gas, power and telecommunication), which represent today a significant cost for industrial operators, specially in Europe where limited areas are available for construction purposes. The use of GPR technology, through precise and fast no-dig areas tracing, would allow timely decisions to be taken on where and how deep to dig, reducing sensibly the number of borings and excavations to be performed, and the high costs associated.

Although these unique benefits should be capable to open the construction industry market to GPR systems, a major innovation effort is still required to overcome key limitations that impede the full commercialisation of GPR technology within such a broad range of industrial sectors. Based on the currently available systems characteristics, and on the state-of-the-art scientific and technical literature, the following main limitations of existing systems can be identified:

- unreliable detection confidence pending on ground and underground conditions;
- coarse accuracy in the localisation of detected buried objects;
- unavailability of an efficient and cost-effective survey technique;
- difficult on-field radar data interpretation, today restrained to expert operators.

The detection of buried objects with existing GPR equipment can be very critical in presence of unfavourable underground or ground conditions, especially for non-metallic (small reflectivity) parts. Unfavourable underground conditions related to the presence of strongly absorbing materials (wet soil, rocky terrain, etc.) or irregular volumetric structures (fissures, cracks, air blobs, etc.) can often occur in typical construction sites. Moreover unfavourable ground conditions associated to the presence of bright radar reflectors and electromagnetic interference at the surface level can frequently arise in typical city environment construction sites. As a direct consequence actual GPR on-field performance in terms of depth of detection, confidence of detection and false alarm rate can sensibly diverge from the nominal values declared, reducing sensibly the appeal of such systems towards industrial users which require clearly assessed and reliable performance specifications.

Existing GPR systems localise detected buried objects with insufficient accuracy to meet the industry requirement for precise no-dig area tracing. Conventional GPR systems calculate the depth of a detected object from the time delay of the received echo with respect to the transmission, assuming the horizontal location of the object equal to the antenna location at the time of detection. This result in an inaccurate evaluation of the object depth and horizontal position, for buried objects located out of the plane orthogonal to the surface and to the radar track.

Furthermore, currently available systems cannot cope with the requirement of a fast and precise scanning technique, which is required for buried object imaging over typical large con-

struction sites. In most systems the survey speed is limited by the maximum rate of the data transfer to the processor or storage device, and coarse sampling grids on the surface must be employed to complete the survey with reasonable time and costs.

Conventional methods for referencing the radar survey to the local ground are based, in addition, on survey wheels, which either place markers along the acquired scan, or directly control the rate of data acquisition. Unfortunately such wheels can accumulate considerable errors over large scans, leading to an incorrect restitution of the ground location of no-dig areas derived by the radar survey.

Finally, a very important requirement of the GPR industrial user is the on field user-friendly visualisation of detected structures, in order to allow easy and immediate interpretation of the acquired radar data. Nevertheless in almost all existing GPR systems real-time processing is kept to a minimum in order to speed-up the survey and reduce the instrument costs. The user is therefore directly faced to the raw image of the received echoes as function of the depth and of the along track position. These GPR images can be field-interpreted to provide real-time information on a site. However, the field interpretation of GPR images may be difficult. Great skill is currently required in interpreting images generated by these systems. Sophisticated processing techniques based either on time de-convolution and spatial migration techniques (adapted by consolidated acoustic techniques well known in geophysics) or on more general electromagnetic inversion techniques have been developed and are extensively discussed in the literature. These techniques are able to transform raw GPR images into more intuitive images of the subsurface structure, simplifying considerably the interpretation task. Nonetheless such techniques require long processing time and large computational resources, and their implementation on-board a GPR would lead to prohibitive costs, precluding any marketing possibility. Therefore the applicability of such techniques remains limited to off-line interpretation of GPR recorded data.

Specifically addressing the resolution of the identified drawbacks of existing systems, the innovation process planned by the SMART-RAD project will make available a high performance high reliability user-friendly GPR system at market competitive costs, bringing finally to industrial operative users the widely known potential of the GPR technology.

1.2. Project Objectives

The scientific and technological research objectives of the project can be grouped as follows:

- Antenna Design and Development
 - determination of the best radiating element design;
 - optimisation of antenna elements mutual geometry;
 - optimum selection of antenna materials and shielding methods;
 - assessment of antenna arrays performance.
- Transmitter and Receiver Hardware Design
 - analysis of technological solutions for the design of wide-band low-noise low-time jitter receiver pre-amplifier;
 - technological and architectural solutions for the design of wide-band low-time jitter sampling unit and the transmitter high power pulse generator.
- Survey control and antenna positioning technique design
 - performance analysis of different antenna positioning techniques;
 - feasibility analysis and performance of DGPS and video based antenna positioning techniques.
- Neural Network based Software Design and Development:
 - development of state-of-the-art two-dimensional and three-dimensional unconditionally stable time-domain finite-element simulators for the solution of

- electromagnetic direct scattering problems;
- screening of data to be extracted from the reflected signal and processed by the neural network;
- evaluation of neural network performances with respect to the noise in the dielectric characteristics of the ground, the geometric characteristics of the air-ground interface and the electric/electronic subsystems of the radar;
- evaluation of upper bounds of the different types of noise indicated which do not affect significantly the performance of the system;
- evaluation of the neural network performance as processing tools of 1D, 2D or 3D data;
- correlation of neural network outputs when they operate as a 1D or 2D processor;
- determination of the way to make the outputs of the neural network interacting with standard post-processing tools;
- identification of the best neural network architecture for the detection of different detectable items.

1.3. Technical Achievements

Technical achievements, which incorporate the above research objectives, are related to the following main project outputs:

- high performance and user-friendly GPR prototype developed within a market oriented system integration process;
- new generation of GPR antennas specifically developed for buried objects recognition and identification;
- antenna positioning system prototypes;
- innovative software for radar imaging based on Neural Network algorithms;
- software for radar data interpretation based on geometrical image data interpretation;
- software for off-line electromagnetic modelling of construction sites, simulation and GPR neural training.

2. ROLE OF THE PARTNERS

The proposed objectives and the expected consequences at European level require as well, to be fully achieved, the involvement of a number of Companies of adequate skill and experience from different areas of Europe. The consortium is composed of trans-national companies and research institutes from different areas. One of the world leading manufacturers of impulse radar instruments for GPR and Research Centres of excellence in the field of imaging and signal processing are included. The SMART-RAD system end users of the Consortium are companies involved in geophysical/geotechnical investigation and non-destructive tests research as well as companies operating in the field of engineering and engineering services. A detailed description of each company is given in the following chapters. The Table I summarise the Consortium Partners involved in the project, their business activity and their role within the project.

2.1. D'Appolonia (Project Coordinator)

D'Appolonia is an international leader in the field of civil, structural and geotechnical engineering services. Its staff, composed of 60 engineers, is involved in research, consultant and

technology transfer activities, with a wide experience in European research projects. The activity of D'Appolonia in the system engineering, coupled to the design and the system integration, has led to major achievements. D'Appolonia engineers have acquired in particular a strong basic knowledge about the integration of complex systems, comprising hardware and software integration and optimisation. The experience of the Company in developing environmental and industrial surveys will help in the phases of definition of requirements and in the on field trial of the system.

D'Appolonia is the Project Co-ordinator. D'Appolonia will monitor the overall progress of the work and it will play the role of RTD Performer, being in charge of the definition of the system requirements and the role of End user, being in charge of development of the on field system trials and system validation.

2.2. University of Pavia, Dept of Electronics

The people at the Department of Electronics of the University of Pavia teach and work in the following main areas:

- electronic devices and circuits, integrated electronics, microwave theory and techniques, communication systems, electronic;
- electro-optic instrumentation, laser technology.

The Department of Electronics of University of Pavia, composed of 40 researches, has specific experience in the following fields:

- o promoting, managing and developing research activity, from the theoretical and numerical point of view as well as from the experimental one, about the solution of electromagnetic direct and inverse scattering problems;
- o theoretical formulation and numerical codes for signal processing;
- o theoretical formulation and numerical codes for direct electromagnetic scattering problems and for neural networks applied to electromagnetic inverse scattering problems.

University of Pavia will develop, on the basis of its long years experience on inverse electromagnetic modelling applied to many fields, the neural network algorithms to be employed in the interpretation of electromagnetic data.

2.3 Malaa Geoscience

Malå GeoScience is one of the leading manufacturers of impulse radar instruments for GPR and borehole applications. The product line includes software and radar systems for borehole and surface systems in the frequency range 10-1000MHz. Beginning in the mid 20ies (direct predecessor) and up to the end of 1998 Malå GeoScience was a general supplier of various geophysical instruments and services for exploration, mining and geotechnical applications. During the last 10 years the company has focused its efforts in the field of ground penetrating radar, GPR. Malå GeoScience is a development intensive company, with about 1/3 of the staff connected to product development and external R&D contracts. The company has 30 employees, its head office is placed in Mala a village with about 4000 people located in the north of Sweden, approximately 200 Km south from the Arctic circle.

About 95% of the produced instruments are sold on export therefore an efficient, international, marketing/sales organisation has been essential for the company since the early eighties. The products are marketed partly through own sales activities e.g. trade shows, seminars,

demonstrations etc. The main channel for sales being the distributor network, which encounters distributors in 50 countries as well as a subsidiary in the US.

Malå GeoScience facilities comprise: laboratories equipped with several electronic instruments like oscilloscopes, pulse generators, function generators, signal generators, RF-generators, spectrum analysers, network analysers, logic analysers, in-circuit emulators and voltage and current measuring instruments.

Besides being an instrument and software supplier the company also undertakes advanced services world wide with the products distributed and custom designed development. Due to the high demands required in borehole applications and the broad range of technologies within an impulse radar system, it has been possible to apply the experience and knowledge to other areas with similar requirements. The custom design development is therefore not restricted to geophysical applications.

They will develop the necessary electronic hardware to implement the new electromagnetic method, which is the subject of the proposal, as well as market the final product and it's sub-systems.

2.4 Federal Institut for Materials Research and Testing (BAM)

BAM is a technical and scientific federal institution under the authority of the Federal Ministry of Economics and Technology (BMW). BAM has a staff of about 1700 people, including more than 800 scientists and engineers working at the main grounds of Berlin Lichterfelde and the extensions at the Berlin Steglitz and Berlin Adlershof. The main guidelines of the federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing (BAM) are safety and reliability in chemical and materials technology.

BAM is engaged in the interdependent and complementary activities concerning Research and Development, Testing analysis, Approvals Consultation and Information. The task of BAM for technology, science, economy and society require interdisciplinary co-operation. BAM collaborates closely with technological institutions in Germany and abroad especially with national Institutes. It gives advice to Federal Ministries economy associations, industrial enterprises and consumer organisations. It provides expertise to administrative authorities and lawcourts. In the area of measurement, standardisation, testing and quality assurance BAM is competent national authority for testing techniques. BAM is co-operating with numerous technical legislative and standardisation bodies in order to develop technical rules and safety regulations.

BAM is in charge of the activities of antenna design, simulation and development. BAM will participate in this project with a group of experts from the Safety of Structure Department, Division of Non-Destructive Testing in Civil Engineering. This group is engaged in development, application and optimisation of non-destructive methods in civil engineering.

2.5 Building Research Establishment (BRE)

BRE is the UK's leading centre for research and consultancy on:

- construction quality, process and production;
- environmental impact of construction;
- building performance - structures, materials and systems;

- prevention and control of fire.

BRE is committed to making its comprehensive expertise and experience available to the benefit of those involved in the construction and associated industries, from multinational companies and government departments to individual architects and builders.

The BRE has almost 400 staff undertaking construction related RTD. It had specialist staff with detailed knowledge of geotechnical investigations, sub-surface radar, and advanced computing. The qualifications and experience of the research staff range from graduate to world leading experts in their respective fields.

The BRE has the UK widest range of construction related RTD facilities. The facilities BRE will be contributing to the project include field test sites, radar test facilities and equipment, and computing facilities. The BRE has specialist centres and staff to enable the development of IT solutions to engineering challenges. The BRE has in-depth expertise in the specification and development of software, artificial intelligence solutions, knowledge-based system development, computer aided design and virtual reality.

BRE is responsible for software design and development.

2.6 Structural Testing Services (STS)

STS is a testing house specialising in the use of geophysical and non-destructive testing techniques within the building and civil engineering industries. They have conducted a wide range of investigations and surveys of sites and buildings throughout the UK. STS has particular expertise in the application of radar in conjunction with other complementary non-destructive and geophysical methods. STS and BRE have collaborated on a number of previous projects. The company sees the potential for commercial advantage in its business as a service provider from the knowledge gained in the RTD project.

STS has substantial experience and expertise in undertaking a diverse range of surveys upon buildings, structures and sites using radar in conjunction with numerous other geophysical investigation techniques. Access to radar systems, test sites and associated equipment for comparative field testing and assessment.

STS is responsible for the testing of the SMART-RAD system on real fields.

Table I: Role of Partners

	Partner	Area of activity	RTD Role in project
1	D'Appolonia S.p.A. (DAPP)	Engineering Consulting Services	Project Management, End-user. Requirements Specification, System Integration and Field Testing
2	University of Pavia (UNIPV-DE)	R&D in Electromagnetic Engineering	Software Design and Development
3	Malaa Geoscience (MALA)	Manufacturer of GPR system.	Electronic Hardware Design and Development
4	Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing (BAM)	R&D Testing Analysis	Antenna Design, Simulation and Development
5	Building Research Establishment (BRE)	Geo-technical Investigations and Advanced Computing	Software Design and Development
6	Structural Testing Services (STS)	Geophysical and NDT testing. Radar Applications.	End user, Field Testing

3. DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH WORK

The SMART-RAD Research & Development process will be based on an integrated and modular approach involving the following distinct tasks:

- Design and Development of new generation high performance GPR antennas

Being the direct interface to the probed ground, the antennas represent the most critical part of any GPR system. New technology SMART-RAD antenna design will be based on the following activities:

- Radiating element design: Damped elements linear antennas (monopole and dipoles), which are most frequently used in existing equipment, show very low radiating efficiency when dealing with the ultra-wide band GPR pulses, and very low directivity gain. Due to this low efficiency only a small fraction (about 1/100) of the transmitted power is effectively radiated into the ground, the rest being wasted through the transmitter/antenna coupling network. Moreover since the transmitted power is limited by the available power supply (battery packs must be used for any practical portable equipment), the low efficiency has a major impact on the system sensitivity, hence on the detection capabilities, especially under unfavourable (i.e. high attenuation) soil conditions. SMART-RAD new generation antennas will exploit alternative broad band designs based on combination of linear, travelling waves, frequency independent and horn radiators, to raise up the efficiency and the directivity gain in order to maximise the energy effectively radiated into the ground, with significant improvement in detection capabilities.
- Geometry optimisation: Transmitting and receiving element geometry will be optimally designed in order to suppress mutual in-air interference, which is a major cause of short-range clutter in currently available systems. Different polarisation will be exploited to minimise antenna breakthrough. Antenna geometry will be moreover optimised with respect to the generated pulse spectrum and the expected terrain properties in order to maximise the sharpness of the radiating angular pattern and time response, which will improve the accuracy of buried objects localisation.
- Material selection: In order to maximise rejection of environmental interference, different combination of shielding materials and systems will be investigated, allowing safe and reliable operations even in the noisy urban environment. Moreover, in order to maximise the antenna-to-ground coupling, the radiating surface materials will be carefully optimised using a-priori information about surveyed sites, in order to avoid abrupt dielectric discontinuities at the antenna/ground interface, which would cause significant losses of electromagnetic energy.
- Mechanical design: Innovative design of antenna mechanics will be investigated in order to maximise the antenna/ground contact in case of rough surfaces (hover antenna). Moreover a particular design based on linear arrays of parallel antenna elements will be investigated, in order to improve horizontal discrimination ability, directivity gain and across track coverage speed.

- Optimisation of GPR transmitter and receiver electronics

Major improvements to the GPR electronics will be related to the re-design of key components, such as a high performance GaAs pulse generator, a wide band GaAs pre-amplifier and ultra fast sampler unit, in order to allow an overall transmitter/receiver bandwidth better than 1 GHz and ensure phase linearity along the full bandwidth. Such wide bandwidth will allow high-resolution discrimination of shallow depth buried objects and minimisation of false echoes. Moreover the innovative design of the pulse generator and sampling unit will cope with an overall time determination uncertainty (jitter) better than 40 pS, largely overcoming the limits of currently available GPR technology. Such low time jitter will lead to an improved precision in the determination of buried object depth.

- Design of efficient survey control and antenna positioning techniques

In order to allow buried objects imaging the probed area should be sampled over a closely spaced spatial grid (grid spacing should be a fraction of the expected buried object dimension), which unavoidably leads to extremely high data rate and long survey time.

In order to speed-up the survey, the SMART-RAD system will significantly increase the rate of data transfer between the sampler unit and the processing unit, complying with systems for fast dragging of the GPR antenna over the surface. Moreover innovative antenna arrays configurations will be studied to speed-up cross track coverage. Antenna positioning techniques able to provide quick and precise referencing of the survey to the local ground will be investigated, overcoming the limits of currently used methods. In particular the following methods will be investigated:

- Wire Displacement Transducer based Odometers (WTDO);
- Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS) based systems;
- video based systems.

- Design and Implementation of innovative neural network processing software

The SMART-RAD project will introduce significant innovation in the processing software, investigating on the use of Neural Network based algorithms for on-field buried objects imaging and recognition.

A neural network is a computing system simulating the human nervous system by means of a large number of processing elements (neurons or nodes) fully interconnected by weight links and organized in a layered structure (see Figure 1). While the structure of the network is pre-defined and fixed, the values of the weights of the interconnections are dependent on the specific task of the network, and are defined by means of a dedicated laboratory activity performed before the field operation phase. This activity is called training phase and is carried out as follows: a set of input patterns characteristic of the investigated problem (training data patterns) is granted to the network and the corresponding output is calculated. By minimizing with respect to weights the difference between the output of the neural network and the expected output (target), the strength of each connection is evaluated and the neural network is specialized to the solution of the given problem. The set of weights which yield the optimum tuning to a particular problem can be easily stored in a small memory and used during subsequent on-field operations, without requiring a-priori knowledge of the functional relating in-

put and output data of the physical problem.

In the SMART-RAD case, Neural Networks will be trained with different underground reference scenarios, identified by a host material/buried object pair and a data base of neural weights will be formed using the results from the training phase. Such database will be stored on-board the SMART-RAD processor, allowing to fastly re-tune the processor following changes in underground conditions during operations.

Thanks to the inherent ability of learning and generalising the results of training, the Neural Network based processor will be capable to give the best performance over those sites for which a-priori information about buried objects and host material is available.

Moreover, the capability to solve a physical problem without considering the functional operator characterising the problem itself makes neural networks suitable for conditions characterised by complex input/output relations and makes it possible to fully exploit the "a priori" information available. In particular, in the recognition of the geometric and dielectric characteristics of an object embedded in an unavailable domain, a neural network approach avoids the drawback of solving a complex otherwise time consuming non-linear problem. On the contrary, the Neural processor will be able to process radar data as quickly as to permit on-field imaging of buried objects and interpretation of radar tracks.

Processed data could be therefore displayed in much more user-friendly fashion, helping the final non expert user to draw himself the conclusions on the composition of the underground layers, the presence, nature and location of buried objects, etc..

We anticipate that the suitable integration of the results achieved by these activities will lead to a fully innovative improved performance GPR system. Nevertheless, each activity configures as a self-contained task capable to deliver significant results without pending in critical way on the outputs from the other activities. Such high degree of flexibility and modularity will guarantee the maximum protection from the risks of unexpected problems in terms of impact on the global project schedule and usefulness of the project results.

4. GLOBAL EXPLOITATION PLAN

Prospective users of benefits within the partnership can be grouped into three areas of business activity. The participants with the greatest commercial interest in the specific areas are indicated:

- production and sale of equipment and software products: MALA, BRE and UNIPV-DE;
- provision of radar surveying services for survey and investigation of construction sites and redevelopment sites: BRE, DAPP, STS and BAM;
- Transfer of knowledge by provision of consulting services and education:-ALL PARTNERS.

Users outside the partnership are primarily related to organisations that require detailed information concerning the subsurface in their capacity as buyers or suppliers. Typical buyers might include a variety of municipal / governmental / utility / contracting organisation with a need to undertake survey and investigation work using radar and other techniques. Suppliers would include site investigation companies, testing companies, and knowledge brokers (such as construction/building consultants). Educational establishments may also be considered as suppliers in the context of knowledge transfer.

Indirect benefits might arise in other industrial sectors and to owners of buildings, historical

sites or monuments and infrastructure assets in terms of the assessment of maintenance and repair needs and the potential vulnerability of existing structures/site in the light of proposed development methodologies. The prospective indirect benefits to the construction industry relate to the quality of information and to improved health and safety for site operators (cable/hazard avoidance) and for the general built environment (more effective contaminated land remedial/cleanup)

In the following table the expected results of the project exploitation policy of the identified project outputs are summarised and listed according to their timing and responsible partner:

Table II: Expected Results and Exploitation Plan

PROJECT OUTPUT/RESULT	RANGE OF APPLICATIONS	EXPECTED IMPACT	TIMING	MEMBER(S) RESPONSIBLE FOR EXPLOITATION
Community Added Value:				
The SMART-RAD System	Target Location Hazard avoidance	High Reduced cleanup costs	1 year	MALA, ALL PARTNERS
Construction Site Modelling	Survey Planning	Medium Improved use of resources	2-3 years	BRE, DAPP, STS
Social / Environmental Impact:				
The SMART-RAD System	Leads to potential new generation system	High Increased employment and improved health and safety	1 year	MALA, ALL PARTNERS
Construction Site Modelling	Survey Planning	High Better targeted investigations improved health and safety	2-3 years	BRE, DAPP, STS
The Technological Experience	Leads to potential new generation system	High Increased employment and further R&D applications	2-3 years	ALL PARTNERS
The Engineering Expertise	Leads to high performance investigation	Medium Increased employment	2-3 years	BRE, DAPP, STS
Technical / Economic Impact:				
The SMART-RAD System	Increased site investigation more accuracy, reduced overall costs	High Market leading hardware with export potential to US Japan	1-3 year	MALA, ALL PARTNERS
High Performance new generation Antenna	Improved performance in buried object detection and mapping in unfavourable terrain	High Export potential of product and knowledge	1-2 years	BAM, MALA, BRE
Signal Processing Software	Increased site investigation more accuracy, reduced overall costs	High Export potential of product and knowledge	1 year	UNIPV-DE, BRE
Construction Site	Transfer of knowl-	Medium	2-3	BRE, DAPP, BRE

Modelling	edge	Improved position in world market	years	
The Technological Experience	Leads to potential new generation system	High Market leading hardware with export potential to US Japan	1-3 years	ALL PARTNERS
The Engineering Expertise	Leads to high performance investigation	High Export potential of product and knowledge	1-2 years	BRE, DAPP, STS
Soil Characteristics Data Base	Transfer of knowledge	Medium Improved position in world market	1 year	DAPP, BRE, STS, UNIPV-DE

The exploitation manager will play a key role in establishing which information will be protected by patents, copyright or trade secrets and which information is suitable for wider dissemination. The information for wider dissemination will be published in various different ways including trade and technical journals, conferences and seminars. Towards the end of the project, the dissemination activity will be co-ordinated by means of the agreed marketing strategy.

In the framework of the proposing consortium STS will play the role of exploitation manager with experience gained through previous research exploitations as leading SME in the field of site investigation by means of radar and other geophysical techniques. The EM shall work with the other partners in order to identify potential commercial aspects of benefits of the RTD project and to seek ways in which these might be implemented. The EM shall look for future development and exploitation opportunities, co-ordinating and liaising between participants and prospective third party collaborators. The EM shall facilitate negotiations with any prospective third party.

In order to guarantee the maximum efficiency of the co-operation after completion of the project a Consortium Agreement will be agreed and signed. The Consortium Agreement will regulate the relationships among the partners during the industrialisation and exploitation phases and, particularly, it will define the exploitation of the project results. An agreement will be set-up concerning the transfer of results for R&D purposes and for future commercialisation of the *SMART-RAD* system.

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